

Tree scale 0.2

Figure S1. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_1 and reference genomes.

Figure S2. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_2 and reference genomes.

Tree scale 0.2

Figure S3. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_3 and reference genomes.

Tree scale 0.2

Figure S4. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_4 and reference genomes.

Figure S5. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_5 and reference genomes.

Figure S6. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_6 and reference genomes.

Figure S7. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_7 and reference genomes.

Figure S8. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_8 and reference genomes.

Figure S9. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_9 and reference genomes.

Figure S10. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_10 and reference genomes.

Figure S11. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_11 and reference genomes.

Figure S12. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_12 and reference genomes.

Figure S13. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_13 and reference genomes.

Figure S14. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_14 and reference genomes.

Figure S15. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_15 and reference genomes.

Figure S16. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_16 and reference genomes.

Figure S17. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_17 and reference genomes.

Figure S18. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_18 and reference genomes.

Figure S19. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_19 and reference genomes.

Figure S20. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_20 and reference genomes.

Figure S21. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_21 and reference genomes.

Figure S22. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_22 and reference genomes.

Figure S23. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_23 and reference genomes.

Figure S24. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 156_L0_bin_24 and reference genomes.

Figure S25. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_1 and reference genomes.

Figure S26. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_2 and reference genomes.

Figure S27. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_3 and reference genomes.

Figure S28. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_4 and reference genomes.

Figure S29. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_5 and reference genomes.

Figure S30. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_6 and reference genomes.

Figure S31. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 152_L0_bin_7 and reference genomes.

Figure S32. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 142_L0_bin_1 and reference genomes.

Figure S33. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 142_L0_bin_2 and reference genomes.

Figure S34. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 142_L0_bin_3 and reference genomes.

Figure S35. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 142_L0_bin_4 and reference genomes.

Figure S36. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_1 and reference genomes.

Figure S37. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_2 and reference genomes.

Figure S38. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_3 and reference genomes.

Figure S39. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_4 and reference genomes.

Figure S40. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_5 and reference genomes.

Figure S41. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_6 and reference genomes.

Figure S42. Phylogenetic trees constructed from 153_L0_bin_7 and reference genomes.

Table S1. Iron related genes in each MAGs

Gene category	156 L0 bin1	156 L0 bin2	156 L0 bin3	156 L0 bin4	156 L0 bin5	156 L0 bin6	156 L0 bin7
iron acquisition-iron transport	2	3	2	2	7	2	2
iron acquisition-heme transport	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	3	3	5	4	5	4	3
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	9	0	0	5	6	7	5
iron gene regulation	7	4	5	7	3	6	5
iron oxidation	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
probable iron reduction	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
iron storage	0	0	0	2	0	1	0
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gene category	156 L0 bin8	156 L0 bin9	156 L0 bin10	156 L0 bin11	156 L0 bin12	156 L0 bin13	156 L0 bin14
iron acquisition-iron transport	2	3	4	5	0	5	5
iron acquisition-heme transport	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	3	2	1	0	2	3	5
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	0	8	4	0	2	0	4
iron gene regulation	9	8	2	5	2	9	7
iron oxidation	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
probable iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron storage	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	5	0	0

Gene category	156 L0 bin15	156 L0 bin16	156 L0 bin17	156 L0 bin18	156 L0 bin19	156 L0 bin20	156 L0 bin21
iron acquisition-iron transport	0	2	6	2	3	2	3
iron acquisition-heme transport	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	3	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	8	6	3	4	5	12	3
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	5	18	0	10	0	8	8
iron gene regulation	5	8	5	11	5	6	13
iron oxidation	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
probable iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron storage	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gene category	156 L0 bin22	156 L0 bin23	156 L0 bin24	152 L0 bin1	152 L0 bin2	152 L0 bin3	152 L0 bin4
iron acquisition-iron transport	0	2	0	3	2	0	3
iron acquisition-heme transport	0	1	2	0	0	1	1
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	2	4	4	3	2	6	7
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	7	7	14	0	8	5	0
iron gene regulation	4	7	13	7	11	3	5
iron oxidation	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
probable iron reduction	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
iron storage	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Gene category	152 L0 bin5	152 L0 bin6	152 L0 bin7	142 L0 bin1	142 L0 bin2	142 L0 bin3	142 L0 bin4
iron acquisition-iron transport	4	4	0	6	2	0	3
iron acquisition-heme transport	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	0	7	6	9	2	6	4
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	12	7	5	8	4	5	0
iron gene regulation	6	8	9	9	7	10	3
iron oxidation	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
probable iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron storage	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gene category	153 L0 bin1	153 L0 bin2	153 L0 bin3	153 L0 bin4	153 L0 bin5	153 L0 bin6	153 L0 bin7
iron acquisition-iron transport	5	0	2	2	2	4	5
iron acquisition-heme transport	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
iron acquisition-heme oxygenase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore synthesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron acquisition-siderophore transport	4	7	2	8	10	7	9
iron acquisition-siderophore transport potential	0	5	8	13	9	7	4
iron gene regulation	4	8	8	9	21	7	15
iron oxidation	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
possible iron oxidation and possible iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
probable iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron reduction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
iron storage	0	1	0	1	2	2	4
magnetosome formation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table S2. Iron related genes in each sample

genome/assembly	156_L0	152_L0	142_L0	153_L0
2514223670 filler {omc} Geobacter sulfurreducens CxxxxCH...CXXCH domain-containing protein [Ignavibacterium album Mat9-16; JCM 16511 : NC_017464]	1	0	0	0
637778189 YP_383877 {omc} hypothetical protein [Geobacter metallireducens GS-15: NC_007517]	0	0	0	1
637864946 YP_466595 {porin} hypothetical protein [Anaeromyxobacter dehalogenans 2CP-C: NC_007760]	1	0	0	0
637864947 YP_466596 {pc} hypothetical protein [Anaeromyxobacter dehalogenans 2CP-C: NC_007760]	2	0	0	0
642557019 CAJ74787 {porin} unknown protein [Kuenenia stuttgartiensis genome fragment KUST_E (5 of 5): CT573071]	4	0	0	0
642557020 CAJ74788 {pc} hypothetical multiheme cytochrome c protein [Kuenenia stuttgartiensis genome fragment KUST_E (5 of 5): CT573071]	4	0	0	0
642764945 YP_002135816 {porin} hypothetical protein [Anaeromyxobacter sp. K: NC_011145]	1	0	0	0
649882260 YP_004151391 {pc} hypothetical protein [Thermovibrio ammonificans HB-1 chromosome: NC_014926]	0	0	0	1
649988567 YP_004281063 {porin} hypothetical protein [Desulfurobacterium thermolithotrophum DSM 11699 chromosome: NC_015185]	0	0	0	2
649988568 YP_004281064 {pc} hypothetical protein [Desulfurobacterium thermolithotrophum DSM 11699 chromosome: NC_015185]	0	0	0	1
ChaN-family-substrate-binding-protein	1	0	0	0
ChuX-family-substrate-binding-protein	1	0	0	0
Cyc2_repCluster3	37	9	9	6
EfeU-family-iron-perase	0	1	0	0
EntS-family-siderophore-export	3	5	0	0
ExbB-family	396	382	312	237
ExbD-family	452	445	362	275
FbpA-family-iron-binding-protein	39	32	23	17
FbpB-FutB-family-iron-permease	63	52	41	33
FbpB-family-iron-permease	25	33	23	17
FbpC-family-ATPase	42	57	40	32
FeoA-family-iron-transporter	72	66	47	40
FeoB-family-iron-transporter	86	68	49	39
FeoE-family-iron-efflux	12	7	10	2
FoxE	1	0	0	0
FptX-family-siderophore-transport	1	2	0	2
FpvC-family-siderophore-transport	21	7	8	8
FpvD-family-siderophore-transport	23	24	16	18
FpvE-family-permease	163	114	97	89
FpvF-family-siderophore-transport	3	1	2	2
FpvG-family-siderophore-transport	2	0	0	1
FpvJ-family-siderophore-transport	1	1	0	0
FpvK-family-hypothetical	2	2	2	2
FutA1-family-iron-binding-proteins	16	12	7	11
FutA2-family-iron-binding-proteins	6	5	4	4
FutC-family-ATPase	26	14	9	4
HatD-family-substrate-binding-protein	112	90	69	57
HmuV-family-ATP-binding-protein	52	46	39	33
HmuY-substrate-binding-protein	3	1	1	1
LbtU-family-siderophore receptor	8	8	3	2
MamA	3	0	0	0
MamB	2	0	0	0
MamE	1	0	0	0
MamK	1	0	0	0
MamM	2	0	0	0
MamO	3	0	0	0

MamP	3	0	0	0
MamQ	1	0	0	0
MtoA	6	2	4	0
MtrA	5	0	0	3
MtrB_TIGR03509	10	2	4	2
MtrC_TIGR03507	19	9	4	9
Nramp-family-protein	1	0	0	0
PF00210-Ferritin_like_domain	146	102	84	69
PF01325-Iron_dependent_repressor-dtxR_family_N	19	13	8	12
PF01475-Iron_dependent_repressor-fur_family	336	301	237	185
PF02742-Iron_dependent_repressor-dtxR_family_metal_binding_domain	177	91	50	42
PF04773_FecR	288	260	167	109
PF09012_sub-FeoC_like_transcriptional_regulator	8	2	1	1
PF13668_Ferritin_like_domain	59	5	5	2
PchH-family-siderophore-synthesis	1	1	0	1
PchI-family-siderophore-synthesis	2	1	0	1
PirA-family-siderophore-receptor	60	47	30	22
PiuA-family-siderophore-receptor	0	1	1	1
PvdR-family-sideropore-export	51	45	36	31
PvdT-family-siderophore-export	73	65	53	41
PvsA-family-siderophore-synthesis	0	1	0	0
PvuCD-family-permease	5	4	0	2
PvuD-family-ATP-binding-protein	47	27	21	19
PvuE-family-ATP-binding-protein	2	2	2	0
PvuE-family-permease	6	1	0	0
RhbA-family-siderophore-synthesis	1	2	0	1
RhbB-family-siderophore-synthesis	1	0	0	0
Sid_PchR_pyochelin_regulator_Pseudomonas_aeruginosa_PA4227_180623	246	314	218	223
Sid_PvdS_regulator_Paeruginosa_PA2426_180620	544	461	333	239
Sid_YqjI_regulator_for_YqjH_P64588_Escherichia_coli_180606	91	137	106	63
TonB-family	144	137	94	85
VabC-family-siderophore-synthesis	1	0	0	0
VabG-family-siderophore-synthesis	0	1	0	0
ViuB-family-siderophore-utilization	1	0	0	0
YfeA-family-iron-binding-proteins	33	16	14	12
YfeB-family-membrane-proteins	48	21	23	13
YqjH-family-iron-reductase	1	1	0	0
Zip-family-zink-and-iron-uptake	4	5	4	2
sulfocyanin	2	2	2	1

Figure S43. The composition of viral communities in the four Kermadec trench sediments at the classification level of family.

Figure S44. Phylogenetic tree constructed by high quality viral MAGs obtained from metagenomic data and reference genomes from four Kermadec trench sediments.